

A NOTE ON THE OCCURRENCE OF "CERYL ALCOHOL" IN
ARGEMONE MEXICANA

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Argemone oil, extracted from the seeds of *Argemone mexicana*, received considerable attention because of its extensive use in adulterating mustard oil and of its etiological role in epidemic dropsy (Sarkar, *Ind. Med. Gaz.*, 1926, 81, 62; Lal *et al.*, *Ind. J. Med. Res.*, 1939, 27, 107; 1942, 30, 145; Chopra *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1939, 27, 947). From the seed-oil, Sarkar (*Nature*, 1948, 162, 265) isolated two alkaloids, one of which had been identified with dihydrosanguinarine, described earlier by Späth, and the other, with sanguinarine. The toxic properties of the oil have been ascribed to these alkaloids. It became of interest to us to study the whole plant after carefully removing the seeds. Investigations on the whole plant were first reported by Schottenberg (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 24, 238) and later on by Santos and Adkelen (*ibid.*, 1932, 54, 2923). The latter group of workers have isolated two alkaloids, protopine and berberine from the Philippine varieties. Chemical examination of the whole plant *Argemone mexicana* of Indian origin was consequently undertaken to find out whether sanguinarine or its dihydro derivative could also be isolated. We have, however, substantiated the observations of Santos and Adkelen, and no other alkaloidal constituent could be detected in the plant.

From the non-nitrogenous fraction, we have isolated a highly crystalline compound, melting at 81°. Analytical data and other physical properties indicate that it is ceryl alcohol. It occurs widely in plant waxes (Pollard, Chibnall and Piper, *Biochem. J.*, 1931, 25, 2111) and in insect waxes (Chibnall *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1934, 28, 2196). The infra-red studies of the compound indicate the presence of a weak hydroxyl band and the absence of any other functional group in the molecule. It has been reported that ceryl alcohol is mainly *n*-hexacosanol (Bill and Steel, *Proc. Exp. Biol. Med.*, 1933, 31, 134) but the presence in small amount of primary alcohols having close molecular weights has also been confirmed in ceryl alcohol (Chibnall *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). It has no toxic properties and has no feeding value and it is excreted unchanged from animal system.

While investigating other plants of medicinal value in the Organic Laboratories of the Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Dr. A. K. Mitra has isolated 'ceryl alcohol' from the leaves of *Zizyphus jujuba lomk*, Rhamnaceae, in a yield of 0.2%, in addition to other products.

The plants were collected just before the flowering stage. The whole plant was dried in the shade and finely ground. Next it was extracted in a Soxhlet with rectified spirit containing acetic acid (5%). The extract was next concentrated. The dark-

coloured viscous residue was repeatedly washed with dilute hydrochloric acid to remove the alkaloids according to Santos and Adkelen (*loc. cit.*). The alkaloid fractions were separated into protopine (m.p. 206°) and berberine, the latter being characterised through tetrahydroberberine (m.p. 168°). The insoluble portion was washed with rectified spirit when the major portion of chlorophyll went into solution, and removed. The solid sticky residue was repeatedly washed with alcohol till a residue of light brown colour was obtained. This was repeatedly crystallised from acetone. The crystals were again dissolved in chloroform and passed through a column of alumina when a colorless solution was obtained. On cooling the concentrated solution, rod-shaped crystals were obtained. From ethyl acetate it separated in hexagonal plates. (Found: C, 81.59, 81.71; H, 14.06, 13.04. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{24}O$: C, 81.6; H, 14.2 per cent).

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